

Continuous Variable QKD in Flexible Optical Networks for Future Quantum Secure Connectivity [Invited]

MICHELA SVALUTO MOREOLO^{1,*}, MASAB IQBAL¹, ARTURO VILLEGAS^{1,2}, RAMON CASELLAS¹, LAIA NADAL¹, AND RAUL MUÑOZ¹

¹Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Av. C. F. Gauss, 7, 08860 Castelldefels, Spain

²LuxQuanta Technologies S.L., Esteve Terradas 1, 08860 Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain

*michela.svaluto@cttc.es

Compiled April 30, 2025

Future optical networks, envisioning the support of 6G services and related demanding requirements, should provide ultra-high capacity and reliable connectivity, ensuring sustainability and security. Quantum key distribution (QKD) is a technology to address the limitations of classical cryptography, enabling quantum secure communications. Continuous variable QKD (CV-QKD) offers potential cost saving and enhanced compatibility with classical systems. This facilitates the integration within the network infrastructure, particularly in synergy with software defined networking (SDN), further promoting interoperability and resource sharing/saving. For the adoption and practical implementation of CV-QKD, it is relevant to consider composable security and a finite number of symbols employed in the protocol (block size). In this work, we present the comparison of two models, to provide a figure of the required block size. We also assess the results using a simulation software. Furthermore, we explore a coexistence scenario considering flexible grid, to exploit the CV-QKD capability of arbitrarily tuning the operating wavelength. This is a relevant feature enabling flexible allocation of the quantum channel to mitigate impairment and saving spectral resources. Considering realistic parameters aligned to commercially available CV-QKD systems and finite block size, we show an improvement with respect to our previous results. A minimum quantum-classical channel spacing of 112.5 GHz is required in a coexistence scenario with 8 x 200G transceivers and 9 dBm of total power over a 15 km link. In case of 10 dBm of total power, 125 GHz quantum-classical channel spacing is required to generate keys for practical implementation over the analyzed links. Finally, we discuss SDN aspects relevant for dynamic quantum channel allocation and flexible network management, enabling coexistence and efficient resource sharing, facilitating QKD technology integration in deployed networks. The presented results and envisioned potentialities of CV-QKD for practical implementation in optical networks pave the way for its adoption in the network infrastructure towards future quantum secure communications.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/ao.XX.XXXXXX>

1. INTRODUCTION

Future networks present new technological challenges to support ultra-high capacity and bandwidth connectivity. Furthermore, critical requirements are imposed, particularly in view of 6G, to achieve environmental and societal sustainability while ensuring reliability and security. Advanced high-capacity transceivers, as well as ultra-wide band transmission, exploiting multiple bands beyond the C-band, and spatial division multi-

plexing (SDM), enable the support of multi-Tb/s capacities [1–3]. Their programmability also offers dynamic bandwidth and traffic adaptation, addressing the ever-increasing and demanding connectivity requirements [2, 4]. Security arises as a critical concern, especially in the context of open and disaggregated network architectures, promoted by Telecom Operators to address interoperability and cost-efficiency [5]. This paradigm is also strictly related to the sustainability of future networks creating

a more competitive ecosystem and fostering a grow-as-needed approach also enabled by the design of modular transmission system solutions [1]. Therefore, in order to advance towards the needs of future networks supporting 6G, dealing with the threat of quantum computers, the coexistence and hybridization of diverse technologies must be promoted and addressed.

Quantum key distribution (QKD) is a relevant application of quantum information theory, appearing as an attractive technology to ensure long-term security and enable quantum secure communications in future networks. It finds applications in optical access and metro networks [6, 7]. It could be used in combination with quantum resistant algorithms, namely post-quantum cryptography (PQC), in order to provide support to quantum-safe 6G connectivity [8]. QKD can establish secure keys between radio access network (RAN) components and ensure quantum secure communications to, from, and between edge nodes, to support edge computing services in 6G systems [9–11]. QKD can be a candidate for securing the backhaul, connecting the edge of 6G network with the core, as well as in the fronthaul/midhaul, considering also point-to-multipoint (P2MP) configurations [11–14], [15].

A QKD protocol aims at the generation of a secret key between two parties, Alice and Bob, communicating through an insecure quantum channel and an authenticated classical channel. The fundamental aspect of quantum secure communication relies on the laws of quantum mechanics and not on computational complexity as for classical cryptography [16]. Specifically, it is based on the fact that the observation of a quantum system causes perturbations on its quantum state. Hence, any interaction performed by an eavesdropper (Eve) affects the information transmitted through the quantum channel. Although the quantum channel is potentially insecure, the protocol permits secure key distribution by quantifying the information available to Eve through monitoring the error rates.

Different QKD protocols and implementations have been proposed in the literature [16], [17]. Among the so called prepare and measure (PM) QKD protocols, continuous variables (CV) QKD employs coherent states (CS) as information carriers and does not require the use of single photon detectors, as needed in the case of discrete variable (DV) QKD [16], [18]. By modulating coherent optical fields, the signals carry information encoded in their coordinates in the phase space (q, p) , also known as field quadratures. These pairs correspond to continuous conjugate quantum variables linked by Heisenberg relations of the form $\Delta q \Delta p \geq V_0$. This means that the product of the quadrature variances (uncertainty) is bounded by the shot noise V_0 [19].

Conveniently, CV-QKD presents similarity to optical coherent systems. Actually, even commercial off-the-shelf components, used in classical optical communications, can be adopted to implement CV-QKD systems [20]. However, specific components suitable for QKD applications, such as narrow-linewidth lasers and precise modulators, together with shot-noise limited detectors based on high-quantum-efficiency PIN photodiodes that run at frequencies up to hundreds of MHz, allow successful and fast operation. Additionally, CV-QKD protocols employ error correction algorithms and the related digital signal processing (DSP) imposes relevant restrictions in terms of computational complexity and time. The use of powerful central processing units (CPU) or assisting modern graphics processing units (GPUs), leveraging GPU acceleration, can mitigate the computational bottlenecks for practical, high-speed CV-QKD systems.

Security proof is a crucial and debated aspect for the adoption of QKD and particularly of CV-QKD. So it is relevant to analyze

it to accelerate the use of this technology in optical networks. To evaluate the security of CV-QKD protocols, the information that the eavesdropper might have access to must be quantified. This includes the information that can be extracted by interacting with the quantum channel as well as the system losses and the information publicly disclosed throughout the protocol. Since this information can be asymptotically obtained with collective attacks, one can give a bound for the expected length of the secret key that is secure in the limit of infinitely many uses of the quantum channel [21]. The protocol, however, employs a finite number of symbols to generate the secret key. Hence a more accurate analysis must include finite size effects in its formulation [22]. Moreover, the security of the protocol must be addressed in a composable manner. On the one hand, the failure probability of each part of the protocol has to be treated individually; on the other hand, it is relevant for the system to allow its composition with other systems [23, 24]. Therefore, both finite size symbols and composable security must be considered to determine the secret key for real applications in quantum secure communications and cryptography [25?–28] [29].

In addition to the security proof, other aspects must be taken into account for the practical adoption of QKD in optical networks. Photonic integration can drive a radical change towards broad-scale deployment and commercial viability of QKD, enabling to reduce the cost, power consumption and footprint of QKD systems [30]. Relevant advances have been performed for CV-QKD [31, 32]. Photonic integrated circuits (PICs) enable the miniaturization of CV-QKD components, facilitating their integration into existing optical networks. Further relevant aspects are related to the sharing of the network infrastructure and the optimal usage of the available resources. QKD technology can be adopted using dedicated dark fibers and envisioning the deployment of a dedicated network. When this approach is neither feasible nor suitable — such as in access networks [7] or when available fiber is a scarce resource — sharing the same optical fiber for both classical and quantum channels could be an alternative solution. This approach would also promote a more sustainable adoption of QKD technology, enabling network operators to offer quantum secure services beyond niche applications. However, the associated challenges must be appropriately addressed. In particular, the impact of high-power classical channels on the quantum channels should be carefully studied and limited to ensure coexistence and correct retrieval of secure keys. Mitigating this impact can enhance the practicality of CV-QKD in real-world applications. The coexistence of classical and quantum signals is generally feasible in the access and metro network segments [6, 7]. The results of previous literature on the robustness of CV-QKD co-propagating in dense wavelength division multiplexing (DWDM) scenarios are encouraging [33–35]. The co-propagation of a CV-QKD quantum channel with up to 39 classical channels, at 100G and 400G, has been experimentally assessed, considering a fixed-grid (standard 100 GHz ITU-T grid) allocation [34]. It has been demonstrated that coexistence is possible with appropriate system engineering, including careful management of total power and optimal quantum channel allocation (preferably toward the upper frequency edge of the C-band) [34]. Specifically, a minimum power is required for ensuring operation of the classical channels, without limiting the DWDM network performance. Accordingly, for allowing both QKD and DWDM systems to correctly operate in co-propagation, the power margins should be carefully identified [34]. In case of co-propagation with amplified classical channels, appropriate

filtering is necessary to limit the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise in the quantum channel. With the increase of the total power, the noise due to nonlinearity (NLI) could severely affect the performance. A suitable quantum-classical channel spacing should be considered [36], as well as a suitable channel allocation [34, 37]. Thanks to the ability of CV-QKD systems to arbitrarily tune the operating wavelength within the C-band [38], this technology facilitates flexible allocation of the quantum channel, easing the coexistence with classical channels and its adoption in optical networks. Indeed, considering a flexible and dynamic environment, while ensuring interoperability is of interest for the adoption of QKD technology in actual networks. This would be a relevant step forward as QKD has been initially envisioned and considered as a fixed, static point-to-point (P2P) solution. Software defined networking (SDN) further facilitates and possibly accelerates the adoption of this technology and its integration into the network infrastructure, ensuring interoperability and vendor-neutral integration [39], [40], [41]. This is also achieved through the promotion of the standardization process [42], [43], [41]. All this is particularly relevant to enable a sustainable transition towards quantum secure communications in support of 6G networks.

This work is an extension of our previous work presented in Ref. [36]. In particular, here, we have extended the security analysis, considering composability with finite block size, to attain a realistic figure of the required number of symbols for practical applications. We have compared two analytical models and contrasted the obtained results with the asymptotic case. We have also verified the results implementing the system using a simulation software [44]. Moreover, in this work, we further explore the required quantum-classical channel spacing in a flexible grid coexistence scenario. We consider more realistic parameters aligned to commercially available CV-QKD systems and finite block size, for two different fiber lengths. Accordingly, we show that further quantum-classical channel spacing reduction is possible, with respect to our previous results, without compromising the secret key rate generation. Also, we discuss in more detail the strategies for integrating CV-QKD with current networks, enabling flexibility and interoperability. This includes SDN aspects and related standardized interfaces to ensure broader adoption, as well as suitable allocation strategies to accommodate growing network demands without significant losses in performance or security.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 deals with the security of CV-QKD, presenting the protocol and its optical implementation. A composable security analysis is provided considering finite block size, comparing two analytical models and verifying the results with a simulation software, for a practical implementation of the protocol. In Sec. 3, the use of CV-QKD in flexible optical networks is considered, analyzing the required spacing between quantum and classical channels for a successful co-propagation in a DWDM system adopting a flexible grid. Section 4 presents relevant SDN aspects for enabling a security layer based on the adoption of CV-QKD technology. This includes the SDN-QKD network architecture and standardized interfaces, as well as the integration of QKD technology in the network infrastructure, enabling the management of coexistence scenarios and the orchestration of shared resources. Finally, in Sec. 5, conclusions are drawn, identifying the evolutionary path and synergy of technologies to advance in the practical adoption of CV-QKD in future networks envisioning the support of quantum secure 6G connectivity.

2. SECURITY OF CV-QKD

In this section, the security of CV-QKD is detailed, starting from the description of the protocol and its optical implementation, focusing on the relevant step of parameter estimation. Then, the security analysis is presented.

A. The protocol

The distillation of a cryptographic key consists on interpreting the information carried by modulated CS. Both parties associate the CV quadrature components (q_i, p_i) of each symbol to an element of a discrete alphabet. For Gaussian modulation (GM), considered in this work, the discrete alphabet corresponds to a discretization of the pairs of continuous quadratures spanning a Gaussian distribution in the neighborhood of the phase-space origin. The protocol consists of the following steps:

State distribution and measurement: Alice prepares a large number N of CS with modulation variance V_{mod} . From the N total number of symbols, both parties choose a portion of size m that will be used to estimate the parameters of the system. The resulting $n = N - m$ symbols are used for key generation. After the transmission through the quantum channel, Bob measures each quadrature pair (q_i, p_i) using a phase-diversity coherent detection [16]. They obtain sequences S_A and S_B of length $2n$ with elements $x_i \in S_A$ and $y_i \in S_B$. The optical implementation of this system is described in Sec. A.1.

Error reconciliation: Following a reverse reconciliation (RR) scheme, Bob selects a random fraction of his measured data and sends it to Alice as the syndrome of an error-correcting code, which she uses to correct her data. They apply a hash function and if their outcomes differ, the protocol is aborted.

Parameter estimation: Using the revealed m random symbols, Alice and Bob estimate the quantum channel transmittance (T) and excess noise (ξ). They calculate the correlation of their data and give an upper bound on the information available to Eve. If the latter is greater than the former, the protocol is aborted. Further details of this protocol step are provided in Sec. A.2.

Privacy amplification: To cancel the effects of the revealed information, they can apply a random universal hash function (as considered in this work) that acts as an error amplification. If the original strings differ the outcomes will be different, and the protocol is aborted.

Given that all steps are completed successfully, the protocol allows both parties to share a secret key that could be used for quantum secure communications and cryptography.

A.1. Optical system

At the CV-QKD transmitter (Tx), Alice generates a train of optical pulses with frequency f_{sym} using an optical modulator and a narrow linewidth continuous wave (CW) laser. Each pulse is modulated in amplitude and phase, effectively displacing its quantum state in the phase space to the quadrature coordinates (q_i, p_i) , so that they define a bivariate Gaussian distribution. This can be done either with an amplitude modulator and a phase modulator or using an I/Q-modulator [38, 45]. In Fig. 1, the first option is depicted. Using a variable optical attenuator (VOA), the modulation variance is fixed to V_{mod} . After transmission through the quantum channel in the optical fiber, at the CV-QKD receiver (Rx) side, Bob uses coherent detection to measure each pair of quadratures [46]. With a shot-noise limited phase-diversity detector, Bob measures the interference of the signal with a strong local oscillator (LO) field. Monitoring the signal at Alice's site, and the phase-diversity measurement outcomes at

Fig. 1. Schematic of CV-QKD optical implementation with Tx, Rx and optical fiber as quantum channel.

Bob's site, they can correct voltage variations for amplitude and phase modulation.

The LO can be target of attacks from the eavesdropper. This might lead to an overestimation (underestimation) of the shot noise (excess noise), and consequently to trust as secure a key that has been generated under insecure conditions [47]. A general solution to prevent this kind of side-channel attacks on the LO is to employ a *true* (local) LO at the receiver site [45], as shown in Fig. 1.

A.2. Parameter Estimation

The security assessment of a CV-QKD system strongly relies on the estimation of the parameters characterizing the quantum channel. For a linear quantum channel, $T_{\text{ch}} = 10^{-\frac{L}{10}\alpha}$ corresponds to the transmittance of a standard optical fiber of length L and attenuation α . Upon transmission, beyond the (quantum) shot-noise, the variance of the modulated signals contains contribution of several sources of imperfections that can be rigorously modeled in terms of the channel noise Ξ_{ch} and detection noise Ξ_{det} [46]. The total noise becomes $\Xi_{\text{tot}} = \Xi_{\text{ch}} + \frac{1}{T_{\text{ch}}}\Xi_{\text{det}}$.

Bob measures the signals with variance $V_B = T(V + \Xi_{\text{tot}})$, where $V = V_{\text{mod}} + 1$ is the variance of the quadrature operators in shot noise units (SNU) and $T = T_{\text{ch}} \cdot \eta_{\text{eff}}$ is the total transmittance, both at the receiver site. The efficiency $\eta_{\text{eff}} = \eta_{\text{coup}} \cdot \eta_{\text{det}}$ contains the coupling efficiency η_{coup} , assumed to be unit, and the detection efficiency η_{det} usually taking values from 0.5 up to 0.9 [45, 48, 49]. The variance of Bob's measurement becomes $V_B = TV_{\text{mod}} + 1 + \zeta$, where ζ is the excess noise at Bob's site that accounts for all noise sources, such as modulation (ζ_{mod}), analog-to-digital conversion (ζ_{ADC}), phase recovery (ζ_{phase}), detection (ζ_{det}), relative intensity (ζ_{RIN}), among others, defining the intrinsic noise of the CV-QKD system (ζ_0). If the quantum channel is wavelength-multiplexed with one or more classical channels in the fiber, the noise contribution due to nonlinear effects (ζ_{NLI}), including cross-phase modulation, four-wave mixing, and also the spontaneous Raman scattering (ζ_{SpRs}) must be considered [34, 36, 50].

Due to addition of variances one can write: $\zeta = \zeta_{\text{mod}} + \zeta_{\text{ADC}} + \zeta_{\text{phase}} + \zeta_{\text{det}} + \zeta_{\text{RIN}} + \dots$. The explicit formulation and analytic expression of each noise component can be found in [46]. In the rest of this section, we consider the same parameters reported in [46] for practical implementations.

B. Security Analysis

Different security levels can be defined in terms of Eve's action on the CV-QKD system. This can be reflected in whether the detector noise and losses can be trusted, so that the highest

level of security also considers protection against side-channel attacks [27]. We restrict the security analysis to cases in which Eve interacts only with the quantum channel, so that the noise and loss at the receiver are trusted. Hence, the attacks to the quantum channel act as transformations to the state sent over the channel.

On the one hand, *individual attacks* and *collective attacks* employ separable ancillary states that interact with the states of light that are transmitted through the quantum channel, and are individually or collectively measured [16]. On the other hand, *coherent attacks* use a global ancillary state (involving all subsystems simultaneously) that is measured after the classical post-processing [16]. Although they are more general, coherent attacks are proven to not be more powerful than collective attacks. Hence, proving security against collective attacks guarantees full security, in the asymptotic limit for CS CV-QKD protocols [51]. Protocols based on CS have been proved secure and optimal among all protocols in the asymptotic limit [52–54], which reduces the security proof to Gaussian attacks [55]. Moreover, non-Gaussian modulation (e.g., discrete modulation) in low modulation regime is close to indistinguishable to one based on GM-CS; so that the security proof can be assumed to hold within that domain [56].

The security of CV-QKD protocols is assessed by means of the secret key rate $K = f_{\text{sym}} \cdot r$. The symbol rate f_{sym} is often in the order of tens to hundreds of Mbaud [45], and the secret fraction r corresponds to the final secret key length l divided by the total number of channel uses or symbols N . Although f_{sym} is technically limited by the speed (bandwidth) of the optical and electronic devices of the system, the error reconciliation stage imposes a stronger speed limitation due to DSP, which would require one or more GPUs to reach the MHz range [57].

The secret fraction (in bits per symbol) is the true figure of merit, it depends on the level of security that the protocol is protected against. One can upper-bound this quantity by considering collective (*coll*) attacks in the limit of infinite quantum channel uses, namely $r_{\text{coll}}^{\text{asympt}}$.

The secret fraction r is defined by the correlations between the data obtained after error correction (information shared by Alice and Bob), as well as the amount of information that the eavesdropper could have access to, through a quantum channel attack, including the information that was revealed through the classical channel. For a one-way RR protocol, r is theoretically bounded from below by $r \geq \beta I(x, y) - S(y, \rho_E) \equiv r_{\text{theo}}$, where $I(x, y)$ refers to the Shannon mutual information between classical random values x and y ; and $S(y, \rho_E)$ is the quantum mutual information between Bob's measurement outcomes y and Eve's quantum state ρ_E . β is the reconciliation efficiency that depends inversely on $I(x, y)$ [58]. The protocol is limited by a finite channel length due to imperfect reconciliation [59].

For a protocol based on GM-CS and adopting phase-diversity coherent detection, the mutual information reads $I(x, y) = \log_2(1 + \text{SNR})$, with $\text{SNR} = TV_{\text{mod}}/(2 + \zeta)$. The explicit form of $I(x, y)$ has led to consider large values for V_{mod} to increase β , however, the SNR can be optimized as a function of V_{mod} to maximize the secret key rate for a given pair T and ζ . Slice-reconciliation or slice error correction (SEC) allows efficiencies well above 80% [59]. In a certain SNR regime, β can achieve values around and above 0.95 using multidimensional or polar codes [57, 60].

Despite the fact that the quantum mutual information $S(y, \rho_E)$ is generally difficult to compute, the Holevo information

$\chi(y, \rho_E)$ provides an upper bound that is asymptotically attainable with collective attacks [16]. Consequently, this provides a lower bound for the secret fraction known as the *Devetak-Winter formula* [61]. Explicitly:

$$r \geq \beta I(x, y) - \chi(y, \rho_E) \equiv r_{coll}^{asympt}. \quad (1)$$

To estimate the $\chi(y, \rho_E)$, the PM version of the QKD protocol hereby considered can be studied equivalently to its entanglement based (EB) analogue if the modulation and measurement devices are trusted [16].

B.1. Composable security and finite block size

A more reliable bound $r_{coll}^\epsilon(N)$ for finite N is obtained by rigorously describing the protocol security-failure probability in a composable manner, accounting for all parts of the protocol in a single security factor ϵ .

Although in general $r(N) \leq r_{coll}^\epsilon(N) \leq r_{coll}^{asympt}$, the bound $r_{coll}^\epsilon(N)$ converges to the asymptotic one "for reasonable values of N " [26]. This has allowed to use r_{coll}^{asympt} as a measure of security for large number of exchanged symbols. However, a relevant word of caution must be considered for the number of channel uses; either the validity of the asymptotic regime is verified, or the finite size effects must be considered, as it will be detailed next.

Real applications in quantum secure communications require composition with other systems besides the QKD modules. This might lead to insecure applications even if their individual components are secure. The security factor ϵ is then defined as the upper bound on the distance between the protocol under study and an ideal protocol [24]. Ultimately the aim is for frameworks in which the security definitions are universally composable. This means that the protocol obtained by composing two sub-protocols with corresponding security parameters ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , has security parameter $\epsilon = \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2$ [23]. Consequently, the security factor ϵ of the protocol must address the security of each of its components. In this framework, to grant *security*, one must guarantee *correctness*, *robustness* and *secrecy* up to a small probability $\epsilon \geq \epsilon_{cor} + \epsilon_{rob} + \epsilon_{sec}$. In what follows, we focus our attention in secrecy, assuming the protocol to be ϵ -correct (ϵ_{cor}) and ϵ -robust (ϵ_{rob}). The protocol is ϵ -secure if it generates secret keys with probability $(1 - p_0)\epsilon \leq \epsilon_{sec}$, where ϵ is the probability of the key not being secret and p_0 is the total probability of protocol abortion [26].

The bound for the secret fraction r in Eq. (1) relies on the assumption that Eve has access to the maximum amount of information available through an optimal collective attack for an infinite number of quantum channel uses. This saturates the von Neuman entropy and allows the fulfilment of $S(y, \rho_E) = \chi(y, \rho_E)$. However, the protocol employs a finite number of symbols N , out of which n are used to establish the key, and $m = N - n$ are used for estimation of the parameters of the quantum channel (parameter estimation, PE). Notably, both $I(x, y)$ and $\chi(y, \rho_E)$, or more precisely $S(y, \rho_E)$, depend explicitly on those parameters, T and ξ . In a realistic scheme, these parameters can only be known up to a small probability ϵ_{PE} associated to the estimation precision. This value decreases when increasing m , at the cost of compromising the number of symbols used for key generation; hence it can be optimized [22, 26].

With the remaining n symbols, the protocol generates a secret key up to a probability ϵ that depends on the success probabilities of each one of the (post-processing) stages of the protocol,

Fig. 2. Secret fraction as function of the quantum channel length for different block size N , $r^\epsilon(N)$ (blue dotted curves) in comparison to $r_L^\epsilon(N)$ (pink dash-dotted lines), based on the model in [62] and [26], respectively. Black crosses and star correspond to simulation results obtained using [44].

namely the error reconciliation, parameter estimation and privacy amplification.

Increasing N might lead to an improvement on the security factor. However, for practical implementation of the protocol, it is of interest to perform securely with minimum possible N .

The analysis of composable security allows writing the secret fraction $r^\epsilon(N)$ as a function of the length of the ϵ -secure secret key generated by the $n = N - m$ symbols [62]. This quantity limits the amount of bits per channel use that Alice and Bob must use if they want the protocol to perform with ϵ -security.

Typically, values for the failure probabilities are in the order of 10^{-10} [22].

The finite size composable analysis in [62] is the most robust model to the authors' knowledge, and represents an improvement with respect to previous bounds [26–28, 63].

In the following, we analyze the secret fraction, comparing two models with the asymptotic values, considering a CV-QKD system with the parameters reported in [46], assuming $\eta_{eff} = 1$. The modulation variance has been optimized in the operation domain $V_{mod} \in (0.5, 11.5)$ SNU, to maximize the value of r_{coll}^{asympt} taking care of the SNR to be within the domain $(1, 10)$, so that the use of SEC allows to assume a constant reconciliation efficiency $\beta = 0.95$ [60]. In our analysis, it is considered that the parameter estimation is performed after error correction [26].

The secret fraction obtained with the model in [62] is shown with blue dotted lines in Fig. 2 as a function of the channel length for $N = 10^7$, $N = 10^8$, $N = 10^9$ and $N = 10^{10}$. As expected, it approaches r_{coll}^{asympt} (shown as a red dashed curve) when increasing N , with relative difference in the achievable length L of 26.5%, 9.7%, 2.6% and 0.8%, respectively.

This model is compared to the one reported in [26], shown as $r_L^\epsilon(N)$ with pink dash-dotted lines for $N = 10^{10}$, $N = 10^{11}$ and $N = 10^{12}$. Both models show a similar behaviour, with the difference that the latter model requires around three orders of magnitude more symbols to obtain similar results. The two models are compared by fixing the parameters of the protocol leading to an overall security factor $\epsilon = 10^{-20}$, compatible with the security factor reported in [26]. The black curve in the figure corresponds to the fundamental upper bound of the two-way

Fig. 3. Secret fraction as function of the block size N for different quantum channel lengths. Solid lines correspond to $r^\epsilon(N)$, dashed lines to r_{coll}^{asympt} and dotted lines to $r_L^\epsilon(N)$, based on the considered analytical models. Black crosses, star and asterisks correspond to simulation results obtained using [44]

capacity of the quantum channel (ultimate rate limit for key distribution over a quantum channel), the Pirandola-Laurenza-Ottaviani-Banchi (PLOB) bound [64].

The behavior of $r^\epsilon(N)$ is shown in Fig. 3 for channel lengths of $L = 5, 10, 15$ and 20 km, showing that it asymptotically approaches the corresponding bound r_{coll}^{asympt} (dashed lines) as N increases. The distance to the bound is due to the fraction of symbols devoted to parameter estimation. This can be improved by reducing m at the cost of compromising the estimation precision, consequently increasing ϵ_{PE} . Here, we have chosen $m = N / \log_{10} N$ so that the fraction m/N decreases with the block size, instead of assuming a fixed fraction m/N (e.g., $1/2$). Moreover, it is of the order $1 / \log_{10}(\epsilon_{PE}^{-1})$ per symbol, yet considerably larger than \sqrt{N} , a requirement for CV-QKD protocols [22, 26]. The modulation variance has been optimized, and $r^\epsilon(N)$ is compared to $r_L^\epsilon(N)$, shown as dotted lines. Although the latter seems to get closer to the asymptotic limit for large N , such values are very large for an actual implementation. The crosses over the dashed lines corresponding to r_{coll}^{asympt} are placed over values of N for which the secret fraction improvement with increasing N , is negligible.

The results hereby presented have been contrasted and verified using VPIphotonics simulation software [44]. The CV-QKD system described in Sec. A.1 and sketched in Fig. 1 has been implemented for GM-CS using the excess noise model described in Sec. A.2, assuming $\eta_{eff} = 1$. The considered V_{mod} maximizes the asymptotic secret fraction. First, the upper bound in the asymptotic regime has been verified and shown as black crosses in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. To incorporate the finite size correction, the simulator makes use of the model $r_L^\epsilon(N)$ reported in [26]. The model is shown as pink dash-dotted curves in Fig. 2 and with dotted curves in Fig. 3. The verification is done for $N = 10^{12}$ and $L = 15$ km, using optimal V_{mod} and the corresponding pair of T and ξ . This is shown as a black star in the two figures. The simulator verification for various channel lengths and different N is represented with asterisks over the dotted lines in Fig. 3, showing accordance to the model as a function of N .

3. CV-QKD IN FLEXIBLE OPTICAL LINKS TOWARDS NETWORK INTEGRATION

The envisioned scenario targeting future optical networks, enabling quantum secure communications, is depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. CV-QKD coexistence scenario with (S)-BVT and, in the insets, case of 200G Tx set, indicating the simulated spectrum and the quantum-classical channel (ch.) spacing.

Advanced bit and bandwidth variable transceivers (BVTs), supporting high capacity connectivity and adaptive traffic [1, 2], coexist with the CV-QKD system of Fig. 1. Classical and quantum transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) modules generate classical and quantum channels co-propagating in the optical network. The channels can be multiplexed both in the frequency domain (DWDM) or in the spatial domain (SDM) [36]. In the figure, only the DWDM case is represented, indicating quantum and classical channels sharing the same standard single mode fiber (SSMF). The multiple channels generated by the transceiver set can be aggregated (before multiplexing with the quantum channel) and distributed in the frequency domain, adopting specific network elements, such as the wavelength selective switch (WSS). Accordingly, the multi-flow transceiver architecture in Fig. 4 can be seen as a sliceable BVT (S-BVT).

For the numerical assessment, we consider a CV-QKD system capable of tuning the quantum channel wavelength across the C-band, leveraging a tunable laser source to operate at any channel within the ITU-T grid. As recently experimentally demonstrated in [38], for a commercial CV-QKD system, by adjusting the narrow-linewidth laser wavelength in steps of 200 GHz, from 193.5 to 195.3 THz, successful performance has been achieved over a 10-hour period. The reconfiguration time was approximately 7 minutes per step, and a mean secret key rate of 15.2 kb/s in the finite size regime was achieved over a channel with 3.76 dB losses, equivalent to around 19 km of SSMF fiber. The capability of a CV-QKD system of arbitrarily and continuously tuning the laser source is particularly beneficial in scenarios where quantum and classical channels share resources. In fact, this allows the quantum channel to be dynamically allocated based on active traffic and minimizes impairments due to the co-propagation.

In [36], we analyzed the impact of minimizing the quantum-classical channel spacing to optimize the network bandwidth usage, when coexisting with eight classical channels at 200 Gb/s (replacing the BVT with 200G Tx set). The considered modu-

Fig. 5. Secret key fraction and excess noise at the varying of the quantum-classical channel spacing considering a flexible grid at 10 dBm of total power and over 10 km link. In the inset, zoom-in of values of interest compared with the case of 15 km link.

lation format is 16-QAM with dual polarization and symbol rate of 32 Gbaud. Here, we analyze the same transceiver set (as indicated in the insets of Fig. 4), and the required quantum-classical channel spacing, considering a flexible grid and more realistic parameters for the CV-QKD system based on [34]. The system is implemented using [44] and, similarly to [36], the LO (at the CV-QKD Rx) is derived from the laser at the CV-QKD Tx, with 10kHz linewidth. It has been assumed that $\eta_{\text{eff}} = 1$ and $\eta_{\text{det}} = 0.5$; the insertion losses to add and drop the quantum channel are set to 1.2 dB each [34]. We assume a lower intrinsic excess noise of $\zeta_0 = 0.01$ SNU, modeled according to [46], with the corresponding optimized V_{mod} of 4.4 SNU. Accordingly, for the same length of $L = 10\text{km}$ as in [36] and [34], we consider a total power of 10 dBm equally distributed among the 8 classical channels. In addition to ζ_0 , the analyzed excess noise takes into account relevant main sources of noise, such as the impactful spontaneous Raman scattering (SpRS), as well as other fiber NLI noise, such as self-phase modulation (SPM) and cross-phase modulation (XPM), which are particularly relevant for high power values, especially when the quantum-classical channel spacing is narrow. To simulate the coexistence of classical and quantum channels over field-deployed fiber infrastructure, we used the UniversalFiber model in [44], which allows accurate modeling of signal propagation and nonlinear effects across multiple fiber spans, adopting split-step Fourier method with step-size control based on nonlinear phase change. An attenuation coefficient of 0.2 dB/km has been considered, and the chromatic dispersion has been set to 16.65 ps/nm/km. Nonlinear impairments have been comprehensively modeled, including SFM, XPM and Raman scattering. Specifically, Raman nonlinear interactions have been modeled using a nonlinear index of $2.475 \times 10^{-20} \text{ m}^2/\text{W}$, a Raman fraction of 0.17, and a core area of $7.695 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$. The simulation also accounted for a physical temperature of 300 K.

We assume a channel spacing variation in steps of 12.5 GHz, according to the ITU-T flexible grid, and analyze the range between 100 GHz and 200 GHz. The results, obtained by using [44], are reported in Fig. 5.

Fig. 6. Secret key fraction (solid lines) and excess noise (dotted lines) at the varying of the quantum-classical channel spacing at 10 dBm of total power and over 10 km link, considering classical channels with different modulation formats: 4-QAM (in purple with square markers), 16-QAM (in blue with round markers) and 64-QAM (in black with triangular markers).

As it can be observed, from quantum-classical channel spacing of 112.5 GHz the secret fraction r becomes positive. At 112.5 GHz, the value of r is 0.0016 bits/symbol, which is about one order of magnitude lower than the values obtained for larger quantum-classical channel spacing. At 125 GHz quantum-classical channel spacing, secure key generation achieves an asymptotic value for r of 0.020 bits/symbol. For a quantum-classical channel spacing of 150 GHz (of interest as multiple of 50 GHz), it can be seen that a slightly higher secret fraction of $r = 0.024$ bits/symbol can be achieved, while it maximizes at 137.5 GHz. Beyond this value, excess noise increases due to the increase of SpRS. In fact, in case of narrow quantum-classical channel spacing, the noise accounting for other NLI has a more significant impact than SpRS, which in turn becomes dominant for larger spacing, as analyzed in [65]. We compare the results obtained within the range of interest 125-150 GHz, with the case of 15 km, appreciating that secure keys can also be generated over this link, even if with a lower r (of about 0.01 bits/symbols of difference in all three cases).

We also evaluate the impact of adopting higher-order modulation formats for the classical channels on CV-QKD performance, in terms of r and excess noise. We analyze 4-QAM, 16-QAM and 64-QAM modulation formats and compare the results in Fig. 6. In the analyzed range of interest of quantum-classical channel spacing, key generation is possible for all the cases. The performance obtained when the classical channels are modulated with 4-QAM or 16-QAM are similar, while in the case of adopting 64-QAM modulation format, slightly higher excess noise and lower r values are observed. Specifically, comparing the obtained r values for 4-QAM and 16-QAM with those obtained for 64-QAM, a difference of 0.004 bits/symbol and 0.002 bits/symbol in average, respectively is obtained and a maximum difference of 0.007 bits/symbol (thus, less than 0.01 bits/symbols) is observed.

In Fig. 7, we analyze the required value of N for the practical case of finite block size. For finite size correction, the simulator makes use of the model $r_L^c(N)$ reported in [26]. With a quantum-classical channel spacing of 112.5 GHz, secret keys can be generated only with value of N higher than 10^{14} . Thus, for practical implementation, we consider a quantum-classical channel spacing of 125 GHz and 150 GHz. In the former case, N must be at least 10^{12} to generate secret keys with $r = 0.011$

Fig. 7. Secret fraction at the varying of the block size (N) compared to the asymptotic value provided by the Devetak-Winter (DW) formula, for the case of 10 km and 10 dBm total power.

bits/symbol, and one order of magnitude more to start converging ($r = 0.018$ bits/symbol) to the asymptotic value. The case of 150 GHz quantum-classical channel spacing is similar with slightly higher values of r . Using lower values of N , to reduce the complexity of the post-processing and accordingly also the related latency, is at the expense of the system performance, in terms of r or supported link length. For example, in [66], it has been shown that by lowering the value of N by two orders of magnitude, the achievable distance is approximately reduced by a factor of 3 with respect to the achievable length in the asymptotic regime.

Then, we analyze the case of $L = 15$ km for a total classical channel power of 9 dBm. With this power value, the related NLI are reduced, thus the minimum quantum-classical channel spacing that ensures key generation is 112.5 GHz. Compared to the results in [36], the required quantum-classical channel spacing is reduced and the reach is extended. To further assess this case for practical implementation, we also analyze the required block size. As shown in Fig. 8, N has a similar order of magnitude as the previous reported case: 10^{12} to generate secret keys and 10^{13} to start converging to the asymptotic value.

According to Sec. 2, the value of required N can be eventually reduced adopting the model in [62] and suitably selecting the number of symbols required for the parameter estimation (m).

Further improvement can also be obtained with an improvement in confidence intervals during the parameter estimation, as demonstrated in [29].

4. SDN-ENABLED CV-QKD

A key research work item is related to the control, management and orchestration of CV-QKD systems integrated in (classical) optical networks, along with their integration into operators business and operations support systems. This wide topic covers many aspects that need to be addressed in what can be referred to as SDN-enabled QKD and optical networks, including the relationship and joint control with classical networks and their management, thus facilitating the adoption of QKD technology by the telecommunications sector.

The first aspect to cover is the control, configuration and monitoring of the QKD systems, enabling the remote programmability based on selected parameters, in such a way that the devices are modeled and abstracted in terms of their capabilities. This

Fig. 8. Secret fraction at the varying of the block size (N) compared to the asymptotic value, for the case of 15 km and 9 dBm total power.

means that an SDN controller can be deployed in a network relying on open and standard data models regardless of the actual CV-QKD system vendor. This concept is reflected in the SDN-QKD network architecture presented in [38]. Let us note that early QKD systems allowed little to no configuration of the devices, once they were initially provisioned and configured. This is improving gradually thanks to the consolidation of open and standard interfaces. The overall QKD architecture shall also address the complementary retrieval of keys, which can be consumed by applications (e.g., encryptors and decryptors) and/or by specific modules integrated into the Key Management System (KMS). Finally, QKD systems are expected to report in terms of their status in terms of streaming telemetry or monitoring e.g., by means of protocols such as Simple Network Management Protocols (SNMP) used as basic telemetry by means of automated GET operations or TRAPs or, in the future, using efficient protocols such as gRPC [67].

A second research aspect deals with inter-working with classical optical communications and networks, and the definition of a framework and architecture need also to be addressed, enabling the study and analytical comparison of coexistence scenarios. This includes not only the joint overarching control of the different network segments (motivated, in part by the fact that QKD nodes are typically collocated with network elements), but also the performance and planning algorithms related to coexistence of the different signals for an efficient usage of the optical infrastructure.

These two aspects are further elaborated next.

A. SDN-QKD network architecture

The fundamental building block of the QKD network architecture is the software-defined QKD (SD-QKD) node. It consists of one or multiple QKD modules (optoelectronic Tx and Rx), the key management system (KMS) and the SD-QKD node controller (also referred to as SDN QKD agent). The SDN networking controller responsible for configuring the QKD nodes (SD-QKD network controller) relies on a set of reference interfaces and protocols to do so. The most relevant interfaces are i) the ETSI GS QKD 014, which defines the protocol and data format of REST-based key delivery API [68] allowing the inter-working of the QKD module with the KMS, and ii) the SD-QKD network controller south bound interface (SBI) based on ETSI GS QKD 015 [42]. Ongoing work also covers the abstraction

models and workflows for the SDN-enabled control of the horizontal cooperation among key management systems, allowing for the operation and management of end-to-end (E2E) key usage patterns. Published versions of [42] provide a definition of management interfaces in disaggregated network control plane architectures including resource discovery, capabilities dissemination and system configuration operations, that is, the interface between an SDN-QKD node and an SDN controller. It describes the flow of information between both entities. The SDN-QKD node part is embodied by an SDN-Agent that collects the local node information.

One implementation of such a SD-QKD network controller integrates QKD Network Controller into TeraflowSDN [69] to manage secure key distribution. TeraflowSDN is a cloud-native SDN controller framework based on a micro-services architecture. The framework has been extended to implement the basic building blocks of a SD-QKD network controller, managing the QKD network topology, along with a Path Computation Engine and modules such as the application register, QKD network monitoring of the SBI towards the QKD nodes [70].

B. Orchestration and coexistence

SDN has a crucial relevance to further accelerate the adoption of QKD within the network infrastructure and to suitably configure and manage the QKD nodes in a (flexible) coexistence scenario. The orchestration enables joint control of classical and QKD networks, by means of a hierarchical network controller (orchestrator) that sits on top of both the SD-optical network controller and the SD-QKD network controller. The ETSI GS QKD 018 [43] defines the Orchestration Interface for Software Defined Networks and coordinates operation between an SD-QKD network controller and an Optical Network SDN Controller. The latter, in turn, may also decouple the control of network elements by coordinating both the SDN-enabled S-BVTs, by means of the agents and the suitable SBI (e.g., OpenConfig open data model), and the SDN optical line system (OLS) controller [2]. Figure 9 shows the envisioned SDN-enabled coexistence scenario.

As noted, a relevant advanced feature that can be enabled by the SD-QKD node controller in a QKD network, where the QKD modules are based on CV-QKD, is the flexible tuning of the quantum channel wavelength. According to potential coexistence scenarios, the appropriate channel wavelength and quantum-classical channel spacing can be selected in order to suitably accommodate the quantum channel, ensuring key generation in presence of classical channels. Similarly, classical channels generated at the S-BVT can be enabled/disabled and their power adjusted, by means of the SDN S-BVT agent [2], for ensuring the coexistence with the quantum channel. Also, given the possibility of implementing not only P2P, but also P2MP scenarios with CV-QKD modules [12, 38], the SDN paradigm can further enable and facilitate the establishment of these QKD links, particularly suitable in support of 6G networks and services. Coordinated actions, thanks to the SDN orchestrator, enable optimal resource usage and quantum secure communication in coexistence with classical channels within the network infrastructure. This is a field of interest, including the development of heuristics and workflows that enable the coordinated dynamic provisioning of classical and QKD services, and the re-arrangement of connections based on network status.

As illustrated in Fig. 9, a critical aspect regarding the deployment of QKD systems is their coexistence with classical channels, both at the control and data plane levels. From the control plane perspective, the aforementioned ETSI documents specify the

Yang data models for the control of SD-QKD nodes as well as for the orchestration of one or more domains, along with OTN networks. Since the specification relies on Yang data models, their usage is typically bound to either the NETCONF protocol [71] for SD-QKD nodes or the RESTCONF protocol [72] for the orchestration interface of SDN controllers. In this scenario, a given SD-QKD node may be co-located with a network element such as an OTN node or SDN controlled transceiver which in turn is modelled using, for example, the OpenConfig platform and Terminal device data models and the NETCONF protocol [3]. In this case, there are several options for the joint control of the QKD and classical parts, and their selection should be based on aspects such as trust models, system integration or separation of designs: using separate agent instances (e.g., with different IP, port, or user credentials) or, in integrated systems in which the different modules (OpenConfig, ETSI GS QKD) are exposed by a single agent. In [73], we have shown from a unified control perspective the algorithmic and workflow aspects to re-route classical and QKD services based on joint Quality of Service (QoS) considerations.

Fig. 9. SDN-enabled CV-QKD in coexistence with programmable S-BVT. Relevant interfaces are indicated.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In addition to ultra-high capacity and reliable connectivity, it is crucial to ensure quantum security, sustainability and interoperability in future networks envisioning the support of 6G. QKD is a technology to ensure long-term security and enable quantum secure connectivity, addressing the limitations of classical cryptography. Specifically, among PM protocols, CV-QKD can provide enhanced compatibility with classical systems and cost savings, making it more suitable for integration into existing optical networks.

For the adoption of this technology, security proof should be addressed. In this work, we have reported a security analysis taking into account composability and finite block size, to obtain a realistic bound for the attainable secret fraction of a CV-QKD protocol based on GM-CS featuring phase-diversity detection and reverse reconciliation. Two models have been compared, showing that a reduction of N of about three orders of magnitude can be achieved. The improvement is also linked to the fraction of symbols $m/N = 1/\log_{10} N$, that we propose to be used for the parameter estimation, particularly for large N , in comparison to adopt a fixed fraction m/N , as considered in pre-

vious literature. The results of the composable security analysis with finite block size have been contrasted with calculations in the asymptotic case, and furthermore verified implementing the system using a simulation software, to provide a realistic figure for practical applications. Network infrastructure sharing, and optimal resource usage can be enabled by suitably addressing the coexistence of quantum and classical channels, as well as by the adoption of SDN. Also, the required shift towards flexible and dynamic environment can be enabled by properly studying the coexistence of CV-QKD with advance transceivers in flexible optical networks. We have shown that, exploiting the capability of arbitrarily tuning the CV-QKD system operating wavelength within the C-band, a suitable quantum-classical channel spacing can be selected according to the ITU-T flexible grid, for key generation in a DWDM coexistence scenario. We have analyzed the coexistence with $8 \times 200\text{G}$ classical channels with up to 10 dBm of total power. A reduced quantum-classical channel spacing (112.5 GHz) and extended reach (15 km) compared to our previous results have been found, considering parameters aligned to commercially available CV-QKD systems and finite block size. We also have found that for practical implementation, 125 GHz of quantum-classical channel spacing is required in case the total power is 10 dBm . The CV-QKD system capability of flexibly tuning the operating wavelength, is a relevant feature that can be suitably configured by the SD-QKD controller, to facilitate the allocation of quantum channels in the optical network. We have also discussed the SDN aspects related to the SDN-QKD network architecture, its main building blocks, relevant interfaces, and the implementation based on the TeraflowSDN, as well as the inter-working with classical optical communication. The evolutionary path towards the use of photonic chip based CV-QKD, thanks to the advances in PICs for the deployment and miniaturization of these systems, taking into account composable security with finite block size, enables practical and reliable implementation of CV-QKD, promoting its adoption in future networks. Further analysis and mitigation of the impairments towards a flexible allocation of quantum channels, in a coexistence scenario with programmable and adaptive S-BVT, allow to enhance the system performance and flexibility. This can be further improved considering additional dimensions, with the adoption of SDM, and alternative specialty fibers. The synergy with SDN enables dynamic and efficient management of network resources, facilitating the adoption of QKD technology and its integration in the network infrastructure, as well as seamless orchestration of quantum and classical networks. SDN can further ease flexibility and advanced programmable functionalities, such as reconfigurable selection of the quantum channel wavelength, and also the support of P2MP CV-QKD links. Together with ongoing standardization efforts, these advancements pave the way for future quantum secure connectivity.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially funded by the "Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital" and the European Union-NextGenerationEU in the frameworks of the "Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia" and of the "Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia" under reference 6G-OPENSEC-KEYS (TSI-063000-2021-61), by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and FEDER, UE through the RELAMPAGO (PID2021-127916OBI00) project. This work has also received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agree-

ment No. 101092766 (ALLEGRO Project).

REFERENCES

1. M. Svaluto Moreolo, J. M. Fabrega, L. Nadal, *et al.*, "Programmable vcsel-based photonic system architecture for future agile tb/s metro networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* **13**, A187–A199 (2021).
2. L. Nadal, M. Svaluto Moreolo, J. M. Fabrega, *et al.*, "Enabling capacity scaling in metro networks with multi band sliceable transceiver architectures," in *Next-Generation Optical Communication: Components, Sub-Systems, and Systems XIII*, vol. 12894 G. Li, K. Nakajima, and A. K. Srivastava, eds., International Society for Optics and Photonics (SPIE, 2024), p. 128940F.
3. L. Nadal, R. Martínez, M. Ali, *et al.*, "Advanced optical transceiver and switching solutions for next-generation optical networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* **16**, D64–D75 (2024).
4. R. Casellas, L. Nadal, R. Martínez, *et al.*, "Photonic device programmability in support of autonomous optical networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* **16**, D53–D63 (2024).
5. J. A. Hernandez, M. Quagliotti, E. Riccardi, *et al.*, "A techno-economic study of optical network disaggregation employing open source software business models for metropolitan area networks," *IEEE Commun. Mag.* **58**, 40–46 (2020).
6. J. Rivas-Moscoso, A. Melgar, L. Poti, *et al.*, "A security plane architecture for ultra-low-energy, high-capacity optical transport networks," in *2024 International Conference on Quantum Communications, Networking, and Computing (QCNC)*, (2024), pp. 231–235.
7. A. Gagliano, E. Mazza, A. Gatto, *et al.*, "Comparison of discrete and continuous variable quantum key distribution in passive optical networks," in *Proc. ECOC 2024*, (2024), Th2A.4.
8. M. Geitz, R. Döring, and R.-P. Braun, "Hybrid qkd and pqc protocols implemented in the berlin openqkd testbed," in *2023 8th International Conference on Frontiers of Signal Processing (ICFSP)*, (2023), pp. 69–74.
9. M. Z. Ali, A. Abohmra, M. Usman, *et al.*, "Quantum for 6g communication: A perspective," *IET Quantum Commun.* **4**, 112–124 (2023).
10. C. Wang and A. Rahman, "Quantum-enabled 6g wireless networks: Opportunities and challenges," *IEEE Wirel. Commun.* **29**, 58–69 (2022).
11. R. Oliveira, R. Wang, E. Arabul, *et al.*, "Qkd-secured and dynamic multi-tenant o-ran 5g fronthaul with quantum and classical channels co-existence," (2023), pp. 1198–1201.
12. Y. Bian, Y.-C. Zhang, C. Zhou, *et al.*, "High-rate point-to-multipoint quantum key distribution using coherent states," (2023).
13. D. Zavitsanos, A. Ntanos, G. Giannoulis, and H. Avramopoulos, "On the qkd integration in converged fiber/wireless topologies for secured, low-latency 5g/b5g fronthaul," *Appl. Sci.* **10** (2020).
14. D. Milovancev, N. Vokic, F. Laudenbach, *et al.*, "High rate cv-qkd secured mobile wdm fronthaul for dense 5g radio networks," *J. Light. Technol.* **39**, 3445–3457 (2021).
15. A. A. Hajomer, I. Derkach, R. Filip, *et al.*, "Continuous-variable quantum passive optical network," *Light. Sci. Appl.* **13**, 291 (2024).
16. I. B. Djordjevic, *Physical-Layer Security and Quantum Key Distribution* (Springer, 2019).
17. S. Pirandola, U. L. Andersen, L. Banchi, *et al.*, "Advances in quantum cryptography," *Adv. Opt. Photon.* **12**, 1012–1236 (2020).
18. V. C. Usenko, A. Acín, R. Alléaume, *et al.*, "Continuous-variable quantum communication," (2025).
19. F. Grosshans and P. Grangier, "Continuous variable quantum cryptography using coherent states," *Phys. review letters* **88**, 057902 (2002).
20. M. Rückmann and C. G. Schaeffer, "Cv-qkd system using a commercial coherent transceiver module," in *2021 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, (2021), pp. 1–3.
21. A. Leverrier, "Security of continuous-variable quantum key distribution via a gaussian de finetti reduction," *Phys. review letters* **118**, 200501 (2017).
22. A. Leverrier, F. Grosshans, and P. Grangier, "Finite-size analysis of a continuous-variable quantum key distribution," *Phys. Rev. A* **81**, 062343 (2010).
23. R. Canetti, "Universally composable security: A new paradigm for

- cryptographic protocols," in *Proceedings 42nd IEEE Symposium on Foundations of Computer Science*, (IEEE, 2001), pp. 136–145.
24. J. Müller-Quade and R. Renner, "Composability in quantum cryptography," *New J. Phys.* **11**, 085006 (2009).
 25. A. Leverrier, R. García-Patrón, R. Renner, and N. J. Cerf, "Security of continuous-variable quantum key distribution against general attacks," *Phys. review letters* **110**, 030502 (2013).
 26. A. Leverrier, "Composable security proof for continuous-variable quantum key distribution with coherent states," *Phys. review letters* **114**, 070501 (2015).
 27. S. Pirandola, "Composable security for continuous variable quantum key distribution: Trust levels and practical key rates in wired and wireless networks," *Phys. Rev. Res.* **3**, 043014 (2021).
 28. A. G. Mountogiannakis, P. Papanastasiou, B. Braverman, and S. Pirandola, "Composably secure data processing for gaussian-modulated continuous-variable quantum key distribution," *Phys. Rev. Res.* **4**, 013099 (2022).
 29. N. Jain, H. Chin, H. Mani, and et al., "Practical continuous-variable quantum key distribution with composable security," *Nat Commun* **13**, 4740 (2022).
 30. J. Aldama, S. Sarmiento, I. H. López Grande, et al., "Integrated qkd and qrng photonic technologies," *J. Light. Technol.* **40**, 7498–7517 (2022).
 31. A. A. E. Hajomer, C. Bruynsteen, I. Derkach, et al., "Continuous-variable quantum key distribution at 10 gbaud using an integrated photonic-electronic receiver," *Optica* **11**, 1197–1204 (2024).
 32. J. Aldama, S. Sarmiento, S. Etcheverry, et al., "Inp-based cv-qkd pic transmitter," in *2023 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, (2023).
 33. X. Wang, J. Wang, Y. Chen, et al., "Field trial of $7 \times 89 \times 256$ gb/s c-band classical / cvqkd co-existence transmission over 7-core fiber," in *2023 Asia Communications and Photonics Conference/2023 International Photonics and Optoelectronics Meetings (ACP/POEM)*, (2023), pp. 1–4.
 34. A. Melgar, M. Iqbal, J. M. Rivas-Moscoco, et al., "Coexistence of commercial cv-qkd and dwdm 100g/400g transmission in amplified foadm-based metro links," in *Proc. ECOC 2024*, (2024), W4A.2.
 35. A. Melgar, M. Iqbal, M. Svaluto Moreolo, et al., "Coexistence of commercial cv-qkd in foadm-based metro networks with full or partial c-band utilization," in *2025 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, (2025), Tu3D.4.
 36. M. Svaluto Moreolo, M. Iqbal, A. Villegas, et al., "Continuous-variable quantum key distribution for enabling sustainable secure 6g networks," in *2024 International Conference on Optical Network Design and Modeling (ONDM)*, (2024).
 37. V. V. Garbhapu, C. Ware, and M. Lourdiane, "Minimal impact network-wide heuristics for the coexistence of classical and cv-qkd signals in the c-band," in *Proc. ECOC 2024*, (2024), W4A.1.
 38. M. Svaluto Moreolo, M. Iqbal, L. Nadal, et al., "SDN-enabled CV-QKD for quantum secure communication in open and disaggregated 6G networks," in *Next-Generation Optical Communication: Components, Sub-Systems, and Systems XIII*, vol. 12894 G. Li, K. Nakajima, and A. K. Srivastava, eds., International Society for Optics and Photonics (SPIE, 2024), p. 128940L.
 39. R. S. Tessinari, R. I. Woodward, and A. J. Shields, "Software-defined quantum network using a qkd-secured sdn controller and encrypted messages," (2023).
 40. V. Martin, J. Brito, and L. e. a. Ortíz, "Madqci: a heterogeneous and scalable sdn-qkd network deployed in production facilities," *npj Quantum Inf* **10** (2024).
 41. "Open european quantum key distribution," <https://openqkd.eu/>.
 42. ETSI, "ETSI GS QKD 015 V2.1.1 (2022-04), Quantum Key Distribution (QKD); Control Interface for Software Defined Networks," https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/QKD/001_099/015/02.01_01_60/gs_QKD015v020101p.pdf.
 43. ETSI, "ETSI GS QKD 018 V1.1.1 (2022-04), Quantum Key Distribution (QKD); Orchestration Interface for Software Defined Networks," https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/QKD/001_099/018/01.01_01_60/gs_QKD018v010101p.pdf.
 44. VPIphotonics, "Available online," <https://www.vpi Photonics.com/index.php>.
 45. F. Laudenbach, B. Schrenk, C. Pacher, et al., "Pilot-assisted intradyne reception for high-speed continuous-variable quantum key distribution with true local oscillator," *Quantum* **3**, 193 (2019).
 46. F. Laudenbach, C. Pacher, C.-H. F. Fung, et al., "Continuous-variable quantum key distribution with gaussian modulation—the theory of practical implementations," *Adv. Quantum Technol.* **1**, 1800011 (2018).
 47. P. Jouguet, S. Kunz-Jacques, and E. Diamanti, "Preventing calibration attacks on the local oscillator in continuous-variable quantum key distribution," *Phys. Rev. A* **87**, 062313 (2013).
 48. X. Zhang, Y. Zhang, Z. Li, et al., "1.2-ghz balanced homodyne detector for continuous-variable quantum information technology," *IEEE Photonics J.* **10**, 1–10 (2018).
 49. S. Kleis, M. Rueckmann, and C. G. Schaeffer, "Continuous variable quantum key distribution with a real local oscillator using simultaneous pilot signals," *Opt. letters* **42**, 1588–1591 (2017).
 50. R. Kumar, H. Qin, and R. Alléaume, "Coexistence of continuous variable qkd with intense dwdm classical channels," *New J. Phys.* **17**, 043027 (2015).
 51. R. Renner, "Security of quantum key distribution," *Int. J. Quantum Inf.* **6**, 1–127 (2008).
 52. R. García-Patrón and N. J. Cerf, "Unconditional optimality of gaussian attacks against continuous-variable quantum key distribution," *Phys. review letters* **97**, 190503 (2006).
 53. M. Navascués, F. Grosshans, and A. Acín, "Optimality of gaussian attacks in continuous-variable quantum cryptography," *Phys. review letters* **97**, 190502 (2006).
 54. R. Renner and J. I. Cirac, "de finetti representation theorem for infinite-dimensional quantum systems and applications to quantum cryptography," *Phys. review letters* **102**, 110504 (2009).
 55. A. Leverrier and P. Grangier, "Simple proof that gaussian attacks are optimal among collective attacks against continuous-variable quantum key distribution with a gaussian modulation," *Phys. Rev. A* **81**, 062314 (2010).
 56. A. Leverrier and P. Grangier, "Continuous-variable quantum-key-distribution protocols with a non-gaussian modulation," *Phys. Rev. A* **83**, 042312 (2011).
 57. P. Jouguet, D. Elkouss, and S. Kunz-Jacques, "High-bit-rate continuous-variable quantum key distribution," *Phys. Rev. A* **90**, 042329 (2014).
 58. J. Cardinal and G. Van Assche, "Construction of a shared secret key using continuous variables," in *Proceedings 2003 IEEE Information Theory Workshop (Cat. No.03EX674)*, (2003), pp. 135–138.
 59. A. Leverrier, R. Alléaume, J. Boutros, et al., "Multidimensional reconciliation for a continuous-variable quantum key distribution," *Phys. Rev. A* **77**, 042325 (2008).
 60. X. Wang, H. Wang, C. Zhou, et al., "Continuous-variable quantum key distribution with low-complexity information reconciliation," *Opt. Express* **30**, 30455–30465 (2022).
 61. I. Devetak and A. Winter, "Distillation of secret key and entanglement from quantum states," *Proc. Royal Soc. A: Math. Phys. engineering sciences* **461**, 207–235 (2005).
 62. S. Pirandola and P. Papanastasiou, "Improved composable key rates for cv-qkd," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.10270* (2023).
 63. A. G. Mountogiannakis, P. Papanastasiou, and S. Pirandola, "Data postprocessing for the one-way heterodyne protocol under composable finite-size security," *Phys. Rev. A* **106**, 042606 (2022).
 64. S. Pirandola, R. Laurenza, C. Ottaviani, and L. Bianchi, "Fundamental limits of repeaterless quantum communications," *Nat. communications* **8**, 1–15 (2017).
 65. M. Iqbal, M. Svaluto Moreolo, A. Villegas, et al., "Continuous variable quantum key distribution coexisting with classical channels," in *2024 24th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)*, (2024), pp. 1–4.
 66. M. Iqbal, A. Villegas, M. Svaluto Moreolo, et al., "Sdn-enabled continuous-variable qkd in coexistence with 8×200 gb/s 16-qam classical channels," in *2024 International Conference on Optical Network*

- Design and Modeling (ONDM)*, (2024), pp. 1–3.
67. GRPC Project, “A high performance, open source universal RPC framework,” <https://grpc.io>.
 68. ETSI, “ETSI GS QKD 014 V1.1.1 (2019-02), Quantum Key Distribution (QKD); Protocol and data format of REST-based key delivery API,” https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/QKD/001_099/014/01.01.01_60/gs_QKD014v010101p.pdf.
 69. ETSI, “ETSI Software Development Group TeraFlowSDN,” <https://tfs.etsi.org/>.
 70. P. P. Tavares, A. González, J. Cunha, and A. D. Costa, “6g qkd network controller for teraflowsdn,” in *Proc. Network of TheFuture (NoF)*, (Springer, 2024).
 71. IETF, “Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF),” <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6241>.
 72. IETF, “RESTCONF Protocol,” <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc8040>.
 73. C. Hernandez-Chulde, M. Iqbal, M. Svaluto Moreolo, *et al.*, “Dynamic optimization in sdn-enabled eons with cv-qkd coexistence,” in *2025 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, (2025), Tu2H.5.